

Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters

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Report on process with accession criteria for the establishment of an inclusive network of European initiatives and organizations

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Executive Summary

This deliverable, *D1.1 “Report on process with accession criteria for the establishment of an inclusive network of European initiatives and organizations”* is part of *Task 1.3 “Creation of synergies with European Initiatives and organisations” (T1.3)*.

The aim of T1.3 is to identify collaboration potential with relevant initiatives and organisations that can contribute to the Mission development, with a particular focus on making links between Ocean and Water actors for R&I. This will require forming a network (Mission Stakeholder Network) and regular interactions with various actors and stakeholders.

This deliverable will give details on the accession criteria for the establishment of the network (Mission Stakeholder Network). As such, background information on the Mission and the Mission Charter will be detailed. In-depth information will be given on the selection criteria of the Mission Stakeholder Network as well as the outreach campaign that will allow increased awareness on the Mission. A definition for each type of target group, as decided by the PREP4BLUE consortium, will be given in order to share a common understanding.

This deliverable also serves the purpose of fulfilling Milestone *M4.1 “Criteria for stakeholder mapping”* and *M4.2 “Digital mapping tool for stakeholder”*.

1 Introduction

Through new forms of collaboration and governance, stakeholder and citizen engagement, the five EU Missions (Ocean and Waters; Climate Change; Cancer; Cities; Soil) will deliver concrete solutions to some of our greatest challenges.

The emphasis on collaboration of the EU Missions at large is reflected in the objectives and structure of the Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030” (hereafter mentioned as the “Mission”). Mobilising a wide range of stakeholders to pool their resources in a coordinated effort is a prerequisite for reaching the three Mission objectives:

1. Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity, in line with the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030;
2. Prevent and eliminate pollution of our ocean, seas and waters, in line with the EU Action Plan Towards Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil;
3. Make the sustainable blue economy carbon-neutral and circular, in line with the proposed European Climate Law and the holistic vision enshrined in the Sustainable Blue Economy Strategy.

Since the PREP4BLUE CSA proposal was submitted, the [Mission Implementation Charter](#)¹ has been launched, calling for endorsements of the Mission by relevant stakeholders. In doing so, the Commission is, in effect, already establishing *an inclusive network of European initiatives and organisations*.

As such, the signatories² of the Mission Charter, will, by their endorsement of the Charter, become part of an *inclusive network of European initiatives and organisations*. This network, the Mission Stakeholder Network, is a way to reach out to and establish contact with potential contributors to the Mission. The Mission Stakeholder Network (hereafter mentioned as the “Network”) will also ensure a deeper, concerted and long-term commitment of stakeholders through continuous engagement.

As Leading Partner of *Task 1.3 “Creation of synergies with European Initiatives and organisations”* (T1.3), JPI Oceans has, in understanding with the PREP4BLUE coordinator and partners, consequently decided to focus T1.3 on boosting the outreach of the [Mission Charter](#)³ and its Mission Stakeholder Network. This is to avoid setting up a parallel network of stakeholders that would fragment the overall effort of the Mission and PREP4BLUE.

To structure this process, this task (T1.3) foresees supporting and coordinating the establishment of national Mission Hubs and preparing a targeted outreach campaign, within the PREP4BLUE internal capacities, towards relevant stakeholders for the Mission

This report will go more into the accession criteria details for the Network, but also outlines examples of how the Network can engage in the work of the Mission.

¹ Mission Implementation Charter – Call for action : <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/files/e31343c3-92af-42fb-8a19-146d61201fea/b16cc951-2f1e-4046-adf8-43fe836df7d0>

² Signatories is to be understood as the stakeholders and actors that have endorsed the Mission Charter.

³ Mission Implementation Charter: <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/MissionOceanWatersCharter>

2 Mission Stakeholder Network

The Mission Stakeholder Network consists of all parties that have endorsed the Mission Charter by submitting relevant actions. The Network will bring together the actors that are contributing to the Mission objectives and create awareness of new ways of engaging and collaborating in order to reach out within and beyond the scientific community and other stakeholders.

2.1 Mission Implementation Charter

The [Mission Implementation Charter](#)³ is a key tool to connect with contributors to the Mission. It is a simple, inclusive, and inspirational framework to enhance cooperation, align intents between partners, mobilise resources for achieving critical mass for the transformational change needed to restore our oceans and waters by 2030.

The European Commission is calling on a wide range of stakeholders, including public and private organisations, national, regional and local authorities (including cities and ports), philanthropists and investors, enterprises and businesses, civil society, research and academia to adhere to the Mission Charter by submitting actions which contribute to achieve one or several of the Mission objectives.

The call for actions of the Mission Charter specifies that any actions at international, European, transnational, national, regional or local level, promoted by public or private funds (including crowd funding) and contributing to the Mission objectives are welcome. Relevant actions include Mission-related policies, programmes, projects, and initiatives to support:

- Research and innovation;
- Evidence-based knowledge and data and/or access provision to knowledge and data, in line with FAIR principles for the Mission Ocean and Waters Knowledge System;
- Upscaling, deployment and replication of solutions;
- Citizen engagement, citizens-science, youth-led initiatives, communities of practices, ocean and water literacy, outreach, awareness raising and participatory approaches;
- Education and training.

While the Charter is non-binding, endorsing the Charter indicates a commitment to working together in aligning and mobilising resources and activities to reach the Mission objectives.

Actors that have endorsed the Mission Charter by successfully submitting relevant actions will therefore constitute the Mission Stakeholder Network. Charter signatories will, as part of the Network, receive opportunities for networking, exchanges of experiences, collaboration and increased visibility through involvement in major Mission fora and events.

2.2 Accession Criteria of the Network

Based on the European Commission's call on stakeholders to endorse the Charter and pledge actions (see section 2.1 above) the accession criteria for becoming part of the Mission Stakeholder Network can be presented as below.

The Charter is open to any public or private parties committed to joining efforts to achieve the Mission objectives:

1. Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity, in line with the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030;
2. Prevent and eliminate pollution of our ocean, seas and waters, in line with the EU Action Plan Towards Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil;
3. Make the sustainable blue economy carbon-neutral and circular, in line with the proposed European Climate Law and the holistic vision enshrined in the Sustainable Blue Economy Strategy.

Adhering to the Charter requires submitting relevant actions. A relevant action is one that matches several of the criteria below:

- Actions may be at international, European, transnational, national, regional/local level;
- Actions may be promoted by public or private funds (including crowd funding);
- Relevant actions include Mission Ocean and Waters related policies, programmes, initiatives and projects to support:
 - Research and innovation;
 - Evidence-based knowledge and data and/or access provision to knowledge and data, in line with FAIR principles for the Mission Ocean and Waters Knowledge System;
 - Upscaling, deployment and replication of solutions;
 - Citizen engagement, citizens-science, youth-led initiatives, communities of practice, ocean and water literacy, outreach, awareness raising and participatory approaches;
 - Education and training.
- Relevant actions shall be in coherence with the 3 Mission objectives and the 2 enablers:
 - Digital Ocean and Water Knowledge System;
 - Public mobilisation and engagement.

Submitted actions will be assessed by the European Commission every month in 2022, with the frequency to be revised in 2023.

Approved actions shall clearly publicize that they are carried out as activities endorsing the Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters. Regularly updating and reporting on progress with approved actions to the Mission coordination will ensure increased visibility and that synergy potential is harnessed.

2.3 Benefits of the Network

By endorsing the Charter and becoming part of the Mission Stakeholder Network, stakeholders have concrete benefits as they will:

- Send a clear signal on the importance to protect our waters by supporting the Mission Charter and committing to promote it;
- Be involved in major Mission events increasing the visibility of their actions and become a Mission Actor;
- Multiply their opportunities for networking, exchanges of experiences to improve knowledge and to disseminate;
- Be part of a community of practice involving entire EU sea/river basins thus contributing to create impact and achieve the Mission goals;
- Benefit from Mission services and tools to empower citizens and young people to take action, by engaging in ocean literacy and education;

- Benefit from a dynamic investment ecosystem and advisory services;
- Get access to Literacy and education tools;
- Be invited to the Mission Implementation Platform services (knowledge, funding opportunities, etc.) and investment opportunities and advisory services;
- Be eligible for awards (through services) for the best cluster champions.

These benefits will be communicated through a PREP4BLUE targeted outreach campaign to raise awareness of the Mission Charter and inspiring Mission stakeholders to pledge actions under the Mission Charter.

2.4 National Mission Hubs

Several of Member States are planning to, or have established National Mission Hubs to maintain contact with relevant Mission stakeholders at national level. While these have not been initiated centrally from the European level (*top-down*), a number of Member States seem to have found such a Hub in one shape or another convenient.

National Hubs could be an effective means for promoting the Mission Charter at national and local level by having a good overview of relevant stakeholders and initiatives and being able to communicate in the local language. They would serve to regularly keep national stakeholders informed of relevant developments and be well-placed for providing support to local actors and collecting feedback and inputs for the European Commission.

PREP4BLUE will interview established Hubs to gain insight into the set-up and benefits in view of facilitating the exchange of best practice between countries, e.g. through a short guideline for the establishment of National Mission Hubs.

National Mission Hubs could be a valuable mechanism also for the Mission Implementation Platform, responsible for engaging with the Mission Stakeholder Network. PREP4BLUE will collaborate with the [TRAMI project](#)⁴ for this specific action.

2.5 Outreach Campaign

2.5.1 Target Groups

The list below outlines the main categories of target groups and the type of organisations of stakeholders to be approached with targeted communication for endorsing the Charter.

- **Mission Initiatives:** Lighthouse demonstrators and Lighthouse CSAs partners.
- **European instruments:** European Partnerships, sea basins initiatives with regionally focused SRIAs, Research Infrastructures across the land-ocean continuum (e.g. ESFRI Projects / Landmarks), Regional intergovernmental instruments such as River basin commissions, Regional Sea Conventions and Regional Fisheries Management Organisations, scientific organisations and advisory bodies.
- **Other Mission related stakeholders:** R&I projects (EC, National), European Initiatives (E.g. Partnerships, Smart specialisation strategies), Global Initiatives (UN Decades), National and regional actors and networks.

⁴ TRAMI project: <https://www.trami5missions.eu/>

- **Research organisations:** Research funding organisations, research performing organisations, and umbrellas of these, in the areas of seas, ocean, freshwater, and the environment.
- **Policymakers:** Policymakers at local, regional, national and EU level in the areas of seas, ocean, freshwater, and the environment.
- **Business/Industry:** Business and Industry stakeholders active in the areas of seas, ocean, freshwater, and the environment.
- **Public funders:** Administrators of relevant public funds at European, national, regional and local level.
- **Private funders:** Investors and philanthropists with a focus on seas, ocean and freshwater.
- **Civil society:** Civil Society Organisations, networks and citizen initiatives with a focus on seas, ocean and freshwater.
- **Arts, media, culture:** Museums, galleries, theatres, arts collectives, independent artists, media, and umbrellas of these, with a focus on seas, ocean, freshwater, and the environment

A contact list for stakeholders to be targeted will be accessible to all PREP4BLUE consortium partners and subject to continuous extension based on the dynamic mobilisation process and response analysis.

The identified target groups largely overlap with those identified in the Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation including Communication Activities (PDEC – Deliverable D1.2), with one of its main purposes being the mobilisation of stakeholders to sign the Charter in order to engage them in activities described in the PREP4BLUE PDEC, such as facilitating dialogue, building relationships and generating exchanges between PREP4BLUE and relevant industry, policy, science and societal stakeholders. The target groups moreover reflect the particular emphasis on public mobilization activities under the Mission, initiatives and organisations with collaboration potential specified in the PREP4BLUE proposal, and input received during the kick-off meeting in Brussels in September 2022.

2.5.2 Outreach Campaign Stages

The campaign will be implemented by T1.5 task leader ERINN, with JPI Oceans as T1.3 task leader coordinating the preparations and input. Throughout the campaign, PREP4BLUE partners will be encouraged to contribute by sharing ideas and promoting campaign resources within their own and institutional networks.

The focus of the campaign will be to broadly raise awareness of the Mission Charter objectives amongst Mission stakeholders from across sectors. The campaign will also seek to provide best practice examples of initiatives who have signed-up to the charter, with the hope of inspiring others to participate while also providing clarity on the types of activities which can be pledged in support of the Mission.

Several of the tools and channels developed as part of the project's Portfolio of Communications Materials (D1.4) will be utilised during the campaign, additional resources may be developed where appropriate.

The identification of relevant stakeholders and initiatives, notably for the direct contact part, for the outreach campaign will be done through the following steps:

1. As a first step, contact is made with the Mission Secretariat to facilitate timely access to the list of approved actions for the Mission Charter in an exploitable format.
2. PREP4BLUE consortium members will be contacted directly and encouraged to lead by example by submitting actions to the Charter at an early stage.

3. Endorsed UN Ocean Decade Actions that have not been submitted to the Mission Charter will be invited to do so through a personalised email.
4. PREP4BLUE consortium partners will be asked to contribute data on relevant initiatives by linking existing national, regional or local databases with the centralised database for PREP4BLUE managed by the University of Southern Denmark (SDU). For instance, WP3 on Citizen engagement has already identified more than 1000 citizens' initiatives across Europe which could contribute to the Mission objectives and which will be encouraged to sign the Charter.
5. Based on a continuous comparative analysis between the PREP4BLUE stakeholder database and the list of approved pledges shared by the Mission Secretariat, SDU will build a dedicated web application where PREP4BLUE partners will be able to find stakeholders that could potentially sign the Charter. This application will provide personal contacts whenever available and will help to design communication campaigns to encourage more and more individuals and institutions to sign the Charter.
6. Finally, SDU may identify further relevant initiatives through web crawling.

The members of the PREP4BLUE consortium will also use their respective networks to enhance awareness of the Charter.

2.5.2.1 Specific focus of first stage of the outreach campaign

The [European Maritime Forum](#)⁵ which hosts [the list of approved pledges](#)⁶ on its website is also providing charts showing how the organisations which have already pledged to the charter can be partitioned into countries, type of organisations, type of actions and sea basins.

This early analysis may help shape the first communication campaigns to reach out to new signatories. Even if the number of pledges is still relatively low, some stakeholder groups seem to be under-represented so far and could be the target of a first communication campaign, for example:

- Local, regional and national authorities
- Private companies
- Research organisations

It also seems important to reinforce pledges with actions in the following areas:

- Education and training
- Upscaling, deployment and replication of solutions
- Evidence based knowledge and data

2.5.3 Outreach Channels

The project website will act as a trusted source and a repository for information on the Mission Charter. In addition to the information already published, further information on the charter will be added to the website's dedicated page for the Mission. A link to the European Commission's webpage for endorsing the charter will be clearly displayed. The website will also provide best practice examples of initiatives who have already pledged action under the Charter on the project 'resources' page. In addition to

⁵ European Maritime Forum : <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/maritimeforum/en/frontpage/1650>

⁶ List of approved pledges to the Mission : <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/maritimeforum/en/frontpage/1650#block-views-86b6c730c95ae29845afccb7120309c8>

communicating WHY to sign the Charter, the campaign will serve to clarify common questions related to HOW to sign up, such as clarifying that an organisation can submit multiple actions, or that an organisation can put forward its general operations as an action.

PREP4BLUE's Twitter account, will publish a series of inspiring and informative Tweets about the Mission Charter, directing stakeholders to the PREP4BLUE and European Commission websites, for more details. To support this Twitter campaign, a series of inspiring and visually engaging graphics will be designed by ERINN to draw attention and drive engagement with PREP4BLUE's tweets. The graphics will be shared with the full project consortium, should partners wish to share information via their own personal or institution's social media channels. ERINN will be available to provide guidance and support to individual partners in doing this.

The communication campaign will be complemented by direct contact, to invite and encourage relevant potential members of the Mission Stakeholder Network to complete the Mission charter form.

The members of the PREP4BLUE consortium will also use their respective networks to enhance awareness of the Charter.

2.5.4 Partners Involved

All partners in Task 1.3 "Creation of synergies with European Initiatives and organisations" are involved in the planning and implementation: JPIO, IFREMER, CNR, VLIZ, SDU, CPMR. In addition, ERINN is involved in the preparation of the Social Media campaign, which will be implemented also with support from WP2 "Creating a Visionary Narrative, Communication & Spaces".

All PREP4BLUE partners will be invited to use their respective networks to create awareness about the Charter. For example, EuroMarine will fund a working group to build an Action plan for EuroMarine to contribute to the Mission & the UN Ocean Decade of Ocean Science. Each PREP4BLUE Partner will also conduct actions towards engagement to the Charter. Inspirational ideas based on these actions will be shared among the partners through WP2 "Creating a Visionary Narrative, Communications & Spaces". All PREP4BLUE partners will also be specifically addressed with an encouragement to submit actions to the Charter.

The identification of general target groups and individual organisations of stakeholders will be communicated to WP4 "Knowledge Management for R&I core: Identifying and Transferring Knowledge/Solutions to Support the Mission", through which this information will be made available to other relevant WPs.

2.6 Milestones

Milestone 8 (MS4.1). Criteria for stakeholder mapping

As part of this deliverable 1.1, relevant partners have been consulted and have agreed on the criteria for stakeholder mapping. Categorisation and prioritisation and further details regarding how to reach stakeholders mapped are specified above. Milestone 4.1 can thus be considered fulfilled.

Milestone 9 (MS4.2). Digital mapping tool for stakeholder.

As specified in section 2.5.2, SDU is building a dedicated web application where PREP4BLUE partners will be able to find stakeholders that could potentially sign the Charter. Based on a continuous comparative

analysis between the PREP4BLUE stakeholder database and the list of approved pledges shared by the Mission Secretariat. The tool is operative and ready to be implemented once the Mission Secretariat starts sharing the list of approved actions for the Mission Charter. The Milestone M9 can be considered fulfilled. The digital tool will be regularly updated during the project to adapt to the needs of the partners of PREP4BLUE.

3 Conclusions

Explaining the network benefits will be at the core of the outreach campaign targeting potential signatories for the Charter. While the benefits will be clearly communicated, clarifications regarding how to sign up will be provided and examples of already submitted actions will serve both to increase visibility of selected actions and to mobilise and inspire relevant stakeholders to engage in the Missions to Restore our Ocean and Waters.

PREP4BLUE is currently working on identifying individual organisations of stakeholders to be addressed through the campaign. Given the limited resources available for the campaign, priority will be given to clusters, umbrella organisations and other multipliers. JPI Oceans, as Task 1.3 Lead, will seek to link national databases to the PREP4BLUE Database for the identification of putative contributors to the Charter. The Conference of Peripheral Maritime Regions of Europe (CPMR), with more than 150 Regions from 24 States from the European Union and beyond, will also contribute to feed the PREP4BLUE database with regional stakeholders.